

MUZÍKA ÁSBAPLARÍNÍN PAYDA BOLÍW TARIYXÍ

Matniyazova Miyassar

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“Baqsishılıq hám dástanshılıq” qaniygeligi 2-kurs student

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Annotaciya. *Bul teziste muzika áspablarınıń arxiologiyalıq tárepinen áyyemgi zamanlarda eki tarlı muzika áspabın qolǵa alıp shertip turǵan adam músininiń qazılma tulǵası tabılǵanlıǵı haqqında sóz etiledi.*

Gilt sózi: *Muzika, izertlewshi, alim, arxiologiya, saz áspab, áyyemgi dáwir, músin, qazılma, ásir, tariyx.*

THE HISTORY OF MUSICAL INSTRUMENTS

Abstract. *This thesis refers to the discovery of the fossil widow of Sumbata, a man who in ancient times played two stringed musical instruments archaeologically.*

Key word: *music, researcher, scientist, archeology, instrument, antiquity, sumbat, fossil, century, history.*

ИСТОРИЯ ВОЗНИКНОВЕНИЯ МУЗЫКАЛЬНЫХ ИНСТРУМЕНТОВ

Аннотация. *В этом тезисе говорится об обнаружении ископаемой вдовы сумбаты, человека, который в древние времена играл на двух струнных музыкальных инструментах археологически.*

Ключевое слово: *музыка, исследователь, ученый, археология, инструмент, древность, Сумбат, ископаемое, век, история.*

Belgili muzika izertlewshisi V. N. Belyaev óziniń «Áyyemgi dáwirlerdiń muzika mádeniyatı»-degen miynetinde -«Arxiologlar tárepinen áyyemgi zamanlarda tasqa oyılǵan kishkene shanaǵı bar, uzın dásteli, eki tarlı muzika áspabın qolǵa alıp shertip turǵan adam músininiń qazılma tulǵası tabılǵan. Ol biziń eramızdıń úshinshi múnshı jıllarınıń ortalarına tuwra keledi. Bul músin hám ondaǵı kórinisler házirgi dáwirde Ózbekstanda, Tájikstanda shertilip júrgen Tanbur saz áspabın kóz aldımızǵa keltiredi»-dep tastıyıqlaydı. (V.I.Belyaev «Muzikalnaya kultura drevnogo mira» L. 1937-g str 98).

Qaraqalpaqstanǵa miyneti sińgen kórkem-óner ǵayratkeri T. Adambaeva da óziniń «Qaraqalpaqstan muzikasınıń tariyxıman»-atlı kitabında da usınday boljawlardı dálillep jazǵan.

«Biziń eramızdıń I-ásirine tán ájayıp mádeniy eskertkish Ayırtamnan tabılǵan «Ud» áspabı, 1946-jılı arxiologiyalıq ashılıwlarda Topıraq qaladan eki tarlı duwtar tipindegi saz áspabın

uslap turğan adamdısúwretleytuğın fragmenttiń tabılıwı bunıń ayqın dálili boladı». (T. Adambaeva. «Qaraqalpaqstan muzikasınıń tariyxınan» 1985-j).

Tağı da bul muzikalıq ásbaptıń súlderı házirgi Túrkménstan territoriyasınan aymağındağı Farpiyan patshalıgınıń orayı bolğan Nissa qalasın izzertlew waqtında tabılğan. Bul ásbap uzın dásteli, kishkene shanaqlı, «Ud»-áspabı bolıp, Túrkménlerdiń házirgi waqıttağı duwtarın esletedi. Bunday uqsaslıqlar, házirgi zaman qaraqalpaq saz áspabı duwtar-«Ud» áspabınıń bir neshshe mın jıllar dawamında ózgerilip, ápiwayılastrılğan túri degen túsinikti bildiredi.

Muzıka tariyxın izzertlewshi alım Karl Engel óziniń «Katalog muzikalnıx instrumentov»-atlı kitabında VII-ásirde Arablar Orta Aziyada jasawshı xalıqlardıń joqarı dárejede rawajlangan muzıka mádeniyatın onıń menen birge ıqsham, sheber islengen hár qıylı muzikalıq ásbapların óz mülki, óz menshigine aylandırdı.

«Arablar Iran, Turan, Túrkménstandı basıp almastan burın VI-ásirde az shertiwdi hám saz ásbapların soğıwdı úyreniwge olar óz balaların jibergen, soñın ala Persiya, Orta Aziya muzıka mádeniyatın tolıgı menen óz mülkine aylandırğan»-dep keltiredi T. Adambaeva óz miynetinde (T. Adambaeva «Revolýustiyaga shekemgi Qaraqalpaq muzıkası» 1976 j Nókis).

Solay etip muzıka ásbaplarınıń payda bolıw tariyxı uzaq dáwirlerden payda bola baslap biziń dáwirimizge kelip jetkenligi búgingi kúnde hámmege ayan.

Ózbekstanda hám Qaraqalpaqstanda kóplegen muzıka ásbaplarınıń túrleri bar, olar kúndelikli turmısta, xalqımız arasında qollanııp kiyatır. Olardan duwtar, rubab, qobız, tanbur, chang, nay, doira, qoshnay, surnay, karnay, balaman, shınqobız, girjek, nağara, qayraq, qashqar rubabı, avgan rubabı h.t.b da ásbaplardı aytıwğa boladı.

Bul ásbaplardıń birazı qayta islenip, yağniy rekonstrukciya islenip bir qansha jetilistirilip, olardıń túrler de kóbeyip jańasha tús alıp keńnen paydalanıp kelmekte.

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